

On the Constitution of some δ -Ketodicarboxylic Acids.

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In a series of papers a systematic study of the properties of some δ -ketodicarboxylic acids has recently been described (Qudrat-i-Khuda, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, pp. 201, 713, 1913). The results pointed towards the conclusion that the acids of the type (I) where both R and R' are either alkyl groups or part of a ring system, exist at least under certain conditions in the lactol modification (II) also.

The effect of *gem*-substitution in promoting the ease of ring-formation is well known. It is, therefore, quite natural that the acids, such as (II) were found to be capable of existence. An extension of the experiments to acids in which either one or both of the substituting groups R and R' are hydrogen atoms, is now under examination. In such acids the effect of the molecular volume of the substituents will not be sufficiently strong to bring the reacting groups close enough and consequently it is to be expected that the tendency towards ring-formation in these cases will be very small, if it exists at all. In this connection it may be mentioned that (Simonsen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 1786) observed that the keto-ester (III) on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid gave γ -acetylbutyric acid (IV), whereas ethyl α -cyano- γ -acetyl- $\beta\beta$ -dimethylbutyrate (V), on similar treatment gave the dilactone (VI) as the only product (Qudrat-i-Khuda, *loc. cit.*, p. 206).

One should, therefore, expect that α -carboxy- γ -benzoyl- β -phenylbutyric acid (VII) will also exhibit properties different from those of the acids (I) in so far as the tautomeric character of the acid is concerned, and instead of the ring or the lactol form (VIII) it will exist preferably in the open-chain keto-form ; and in that case if the acid were to be heated above its melting point, unlike its isomer (I), it will yield the monobasic acid (IX) alone with the loss of carbon dioxide. And on similar considerations it may be concluded that in the keto-acid (IX) there will be very little tendency to undergo the tautomeric change to enable it to exist as the lactol (X) in the free state.

(VII)

(VIII)

(IX)

(X)

In a recent publication (Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 321) describes the acid (VII) as the lactol acid (VIII), assigns the ring formula (X) to the keto-monobasic acid (IX) and goes on generalising the same conclusion for a series of acids of similar constitution. It appeared to the author rather peculiar that this should be the case. And hence although it formed a part of the original scheme to study the behaviour of these acids along with other monosubstituted acids of this type, it was thought desirable to examine the constitution of at least some of these acids without further delay. A study has accordingly been made into the constitution of α -carboxy- γ -benzoyl- β -phenylbutyric and α -carboxy- γ -acetyl- β -phenylbutyric acids and it is found that the observations of Barat are inaccurate and his conclusions appear to be based on an imperfect knowledge of the author's work on keto-lactol tautomerism. It may be mentioned here that this work is being continued in extension of the series of papers already published by the present author and that the former may not extend the studies of

these acids and the products of their bromination specially in these lines.

It is an obvious fact that δ -hydroxy acids undergo decomposition very readily with the formation of lactones (compare Qudrati-Khuda, *loc. cit.*, p. 201). Hence the acid (VII), if it were to exist as (VIII), should yield the corresponding dilactone (XI), on being heated alone, as the only product of decomposition. But the experimental observations are contrary to this expectation; no neutral product could be isolated by the decomposition of the acid (VII), which on heating loses carbon dioxide and is completely converted into the keto-monobasic acid (IX). An attempt to convert the dibasic acid (VII) into the corresponding dilactone with dehydrating agents, such as acetyl chloride was unsuccessful, the acid after being refluxed with an excess of the reagent was recovered unchanged, thus proving that the carbonyl and the carboxyl groups in the molecule are so far apart that there is hardly any tendency here towards ring formation; had it existed in the lactol form (VIII) it should have given a dilactone or else an acetyl derivative but the acid recovered on pouring the above reaction mixture into water, melted at the same temperature as that with which the start was made. Moreover this acid on esterification with methyl alcoholic sulphuric acid yielded the normal ester, m.p. 108° , identical with the product of condensation of dimethyl malonate and styrylphenylketone and not the methoxy ester (XII), which should result from (VIII).

(XI)

(XII)

Mannich and Butz (*Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 456) prepared a neutral product from the dicarboxylic acid (VII) with thionyl chloride and they described it as the anhydride (XIII). This, however, might have been the dilactone (XI) but its reactions as described by them are not shared by the latter. This neutral product, for example, when boiled with absolute alcohol yields the acid ester (XIV) and with ammonia the amic acid (XV) is obtained; the dilactones so far known do not undergo such decompositions. These observations may

be taken as lending further support to the fact that the acid (VII) is not capable of existing in the lactol modification (VIII) at all.

Barat's deductions regarding the ring structure of the keto-acid (IX) appear to be based on the observation that the keto-monobasic acid (IX) did not dissolve in a solution of sodium bicarbonate but a sample of this acid prepared from the dibasic acid (VII) by decomposition is now found to dissolve completely in this solvent, only that the acid should be powdered well before being treated with the solvent. The acid obtained from the bicarbonate solution on acidification melts at the same temperature as the original acid.

A similar acid, γ -acetyl- β -phenylbutyric acid (XVI) has been described by Vorländer and Knotzsch (*Annalen*, 1897, 294, 317) who prepared its oxime, also esterified the acid with alcoholic mineral acid and obtained the normal ester, which yielded phenyldihydroresorcinol after the necessary treatment. If the acid were to exist in the isomeric lactol form, here also, instead of the normal ester, the ethoxy ester (XVII) should have resulted on esterification, which would be incapable of giving the dihydroresorcinol derivative. The acid (XVI) has also been prepared and found to be soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution like its other homologue. It may, therefore, be concluded that the assumption of a ring structure for these and similar acids is untenable.

For the preparation of the acid (VII), the corresponding dimethyl ester was hydrolysed with 15% potassium hydroxide solution, the ester being very conveniently prepared by the method described in the experimental portion.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dimethyl α -Carboxy- γ -benzoyl- β -phenylbutyrate.—Sodium (0.2 g.) was dissolved in 30 c.c. of methyl alcohol and dimethyl malonate (13 g.) was poured into this. Styrylphenylketone (20 g.) was then added to the mixture and the whole was shaken vigorously. In two to three minutes the ketone goes into solution and the mixture becomes hot; crystals then begin to separate and the whole sets to a solid mass. It was left overnight and the solid was then filtered off, washed first with a small amount of methyl alcohol and then thoroughly with water. The ester crystallises well from alcohol and melts at 108° (yield 26.5 g.). The *semicarbazone* separates on heating a solution of semicarbazide acetate and the keto-ester for about three quarters of an hour on the water-bath. It crystallises from dilute alcohol or a mixture of benzene and petroleum and melts at 143°. (Found: C, 64.0; H, 5.6. $C_{21}H_{23}O_5N_3$ requires C, 63.5; H, 5.7 per cent.).

α -Carboxy- γ -benzoyl- β -phenylbutyric Acid.—The above ester (10 g.) was mixed with potassium hydroxide (6 g.) in 20 c.c. of water and 12 c.c. of alcohol. The mixture was heated under reflux for $\frac{3}{4}$ —1 hour, then cooled and diluted largely with water. The smell of styrylphenylketone was perceptible at this stage and a small amount of yellow precipitate was formed, probably due to reversible decomposition in the presence of alkali. The solution was filtered off and acidified with hydrochloric acid, when the acid (VII) was precipitated out. It was filtered, washed and crystallised from aqueous alcohol, a mixture of chloroform and acetone or benzene and methyl alcohol, when it melted at 148° (decomp.) (yield 7.8 g.).

Behaviour of the Acid (VII) on Heating.—The acid (4.5 g.) was heated alone at 160-70° for about half an hour when the decomposition was complete. The melt was cooled and treated with a solution of sodium carbonate, in which it dissolved completely. The acid was precipitated with hydrochloric acid, filtered, washed and

dried when it weighed 3.2 g. It crystallises well from dilute acetic acid and melts at 160°. (Found: M. W. by titration, 267. Calc. M. W. 268). The *semicarbazone* separates from alcohol and melts at 220°. (Found: C, 66.8; H, 5.9. $C_{18}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires C, 66.5; H, 5.8 per cent.). (Barat gives the melting point as 215° and no analysis; the semicarbazone melting at this temperature appears to contain some unchanged acid along with it which is rather difficult to separate).

Dimethyl α -Carboxy- γ -acetyl- β -phenylbutyrate.—Styrylmethylketone (14 g.) was added to a mixture of dimethyl malonate (13.5 g.) and a solution of sodium (0.2 g.) in dry methyl alcohol (40 c.c.). The mixture was shaken and in a few minutes the solution became warm; this was then heated on the water-bath for an hour and a half, allowed to stand overnight and then the solvent removed by evaporation. The residue was diluted with water, the oily precipitate taken up in ether, dried and the solvent evaporated off slowly, when some solid separated in beautiful rhombic cubes. This was triturated with petroleum (b. p. 75-95°) and filtered off. The ester crystallises from a mixture of ether and petroleum and melts at 65° (yield 19.5 g.) (compare Kohler and Allen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 1987). The *semicarbazone* crystallises from very dilute alcohol and melts at 118°. (Found: C, 57.5; H, 6.0. $C_{16}H_{21}O_5N_3$ requires C, 57.3; H, 6.2 per cent.).

α -Carboxy- γ -acetyl- β -phenylbutyric acid was prepared by hydrolysing the above ester (10 g.) with a solution of potassium hydroxide (5 g.) in 30 c.c. of water and 10 c.c. of alcohol. It was warmed to make the solution homogeneous and then left at the ordinary temperature for about 20 hours. The alkaline solution was diluted, extracted with ether, then acidified and the solution saturated with ammonium chloride when the acid was precipitated as an oil; this was taken up in ether, dried and the solvent removed. The residual oil solidified on leaving in an evacuated desiccator. It crystallises in slender silky needles from a mixture of ether and petroleum and melts at 115°. (Found: C, 62.6; H, 5.4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.6 per cent.). (compare Vorländer and Knotzsch, *loc. cit.*). The acid was recovered unchanged after being treated with acetyl chloride.

The above dibasic acid decomposes completely, on being heated at 160-65° for about two hours with the elimination of carbon

dioxide only. The melt solidified on cooling and dissolved completely in a solution of sodium carbonate from which γ -acetyl- β -phenylbutyric acid was obtained on acidification. It crystallises in clusters of flattened needles from a mixture of benzene and petroleum (b. p. 75-95° and melts at 85°. (Found: M. W. by titration, 206. Calc. M.W. 206). The acid dissolves completely in a solution of sodium bicarbonate and gives a *semicarbazone* which crystallises from dilute alcohol in nodules and melts at 171.5°. (Found: C, 59.1; H, 6.3. $C_{13}H_{17}O_3N_3$ requires C, 59.3; H, 6.4 per cent.).

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